

Tuning Ce_{1-x}Er_xO₃-based COMpounds as effective catalyst for Electrochemical Cells

PROPOSAL ACRONYM : CECOMECEC

<https://cecomec.wordpress.com>

Proposal summary

The aim of this project is to investigate the influence of double doping on the electrochemical activity of ceria-based compounds that can act as catalysts for fuel electrodes in Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC)/Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOEC). The studies will be based on structural characterization techniques at the microscopic scale (XAS) and chemical characterizations coupled to 'operando' data collection. The research will be carried out as a collaboration between the LISA beamline and the Gdansk University of Technology (Gdansk Tech). The electrodes will be prepared and characterized from an electrochemical point of view in Gdansk whereas the structural characterizations will be carried out at ESRF (LISA) and SOLARIS (beamlines DEMETER- STXM branch and PolyX) synchrotrons. The project is financed by CERIC-ERIC and co-financed by the partners; the total envelope is about 381 k€.

Scientific and technical program

CeO_{2-δ} compounds exhibit interesting ion transport properties that strongly depend on the microstructure and the on presence of dopants and impurities. Such flexibility makes them interesting candidates e.g. for catalytic materials working on the anode side of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells, significantly affecting the process of direct internal reforming of biogas and limiting the carbon deposition process on the fuel cell. Using Ceria it is also possible to exsolve metallic nanoparticles to the surface of its grains. In this process, occurring in reducing conditions, some cations from within the host compound migrate in the form of nanoparticles towards the oxide surface. The exsolution method offers even distribution of particles as well as improved attachment to the host material. The resulting material possess structural aspects at the microscale (incorporation site of the dopants) and at the mesoscale (nanoparticles) both contributing to the overall behaviour. Understanding the link between transport properties and micro/meso-structure in CeO_{2-δ} doped with rare earths (RE: La,Gd,Pr,Sm) and transition metals (TM: Ni/Fe/Co/Cu) will be the object of CECOMECEC. The studies will focus on the local structure around dopants in cerium oxide – based electrodes and on the elemental distribution in the material and will put the results in relation with the overall electrochemical behavior of the electrode itself. The preparation of the samples and their characterization in the reactors/cells will be carried out in Gdansk whereas the micro structural characterization via the XAS and XRD techniques will be carried out at LISA and the meso-structural characterization via STXM, μ XAFS and μ XRF experiments will be performed at SOLARIS. LISA and its project office, in collaboration with Gdansk Tech, will design and realize reaction cells for operando measurements with the XAS and XRD techniques. Gdansk Tech will also perform the non-equilibrium chemical analysis of reaction cells with ceria-based electrodes to determine their influence on electrochemical activity of the system. Such a complex approach containing the technological contribution (synthesis of materials, application in reaction cells), analysis of the local structure (also in operando conditions) as well as deep insight view at the

role of metal-ceria interfaces will provide a brand-new knowledge about this group of materials and will indicate a direction for future applications.

Impact

This project will first of all shed a light on the effect of various Rare Earth and Transition Metal dopants on the overall behavior of ceria-based electrodes, in particular by linking their local structure and chemistry with the overall catalytic efficiency. Although rare earth dopants to ceria are known to have a positive impact on the long-term stability of SOFC fueled by biogas, as well as transition metals are known to increase the electrocatalytic performance of SOFC/SOEC, there is no clear evidence explaining the origin of these improvements. It is expected to be a sum of the high oxygen storage capacity of ceria, providing charge neutrality conditions due to doping and changing oxidation state in reducing conditions, formation of nanometallic precipitates acting as catalytic centers, a role of metal-cerium interface etc. Understanding the role of additives to ceria, particularly in the case of double doping, will allow tailoring future properties of fabricated compounds to make them more efficient for electrochemical applications. Moreover, this will allow the realization of parts of instrumentation like ad-hoc reaction cells for synchrotron experiments in operando conditions (and the related design plans) and that that will remain available for the users of the beamlines at ESRF and SOLARIS with a resulting increased capability of materials characterization of the CERIC instruments.

Implementation

For this research, the nanocrystalline materials for electrodes will be prepared at the Gdansk Tech under the supervision of prof B. Bochentyn following the wet synthesis methods (e.g. Pechini, co-precipitation or reverse microemulsion) and characterized from the application point of view via XRD, SEM, BET, dilatometry, as well as by measurements of electrical conductivity and catalytic activity led in the catalytic reactor combined with GC. The group in Gdansk and LISA will design the reaction cells for the analysis in operando conditions and these cells will be realized either at the Gdansk University of Technology or in Grenoble. The materials synthesized within this project will be examined on the fuel electrode side towards their resistivity vs. carbon deposition and poisoning by contaminants present in the fuel. A non-equilibrium chemical analysis of outlet gases will give an answer on the direction and predominance of peculiar reforming reactions happening on the fuel electrode during supplying some alternative, environmentally friendly fuels (e.g. biogas, ethanol etc.). Reaction cells for experiment in operando conditions could be possibly designed with the support of the project office of the CNR-IOM institute, the headquarters of the LISA beamline.

The activity at LISA will be focused on the microscopic characterization of the electrodes in both ex-situ and operando conditions with the techniques XAS and XRD. The extreme flexibility of the beamline will permit the analysis of the Transition Metals as well as Rare Earth elements at both the L_3 and K edges. In this case, the activity will consist in collecting and analyzing XAS data (FEFF code) and carry out the ab initio structural simulation for their interpretation, as well as to define the procedures for the experiments in operando conditions. Using the computing cluster available at the ESRF site it will also be possible to carry out structural simulation via Density Functional Theory (VASP code) or Molecular Dynamics (GROMACS, VASP codes). An amount of 30 shifts per year will be ensured for the

realization of the research. Additional shifts could be awarded with the standard user access procedures.

At SOLARIS, 15 shifts per year at PolyX and DEMETER be allocated for the realization of the studies. These instruments will provide the morphological information (shape, composition, element distribution of nanostructures) at a larger scale (several nm to μm) in order to complement the microstructural information derived from XAS and XRD as well as will provide selective XAS information not available at LISA. Additional beamtime will be possible by means of standard beamtime application procedures.

The timeline will be as follows:

- 1 semester - preparation of a first batch of samples from a group of $(\text{Ce,RE,TM})\text{O}_{2-6}$ (where RE=La,Gd,Pr,Sm and TM=Co,Cu,Fe,Mn,Ni) and characterization of their microstructure, thermal expansion, as well as electrical and catalytic properties. Selection of the most promising compounds for further experiments.
- 2 semester - characterization ex-situ via EXAFS and XRD at LISA and determination of the conditions for the operando measurements. Data analysis and initial ab initio structural simulations.
- 3 semester - characterization ex-situ via STXM and μXAS at SOLARIS. Preparation of the second batch of samples.
- 4 semester - fabrication of the reaction cells and tests in operando mode. Presentation of first data at international conferences.
- 5 semester – post-mortem analysis via EXAFS/XRD at LISA and STXM and μXAS at SOLARIS. Data analysis and second run of ab initio structural simulations.
- 6 semester – results summary. Description of the influence of dopants on the properties of the compounds produced. Selection of the most optimal doping for applications in electrochemical cells.

The costs of this project will include the salary for a post-doc scientist and the cost for trips Grenoble/ Gdansk Tech/ SOLARIS for the realization of the experiments. Moreover, an appreciable part will be devoted to the consumables to be used for the realization of the reaction cells and reagents for the electrodes preparation. The results of the research will be disseminated in peer reviewed international journals adopting the “open access” mode (a part of the budget will be dedicated to that) as well as via presentations at international conferences. All the data will be collected in observance to the FAIR standard as it is implemented at the ESRF and will be of public domain after 5 years from collection.